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ASSESSMENT OF NOISE POLLUTION AND THE PERCEIVED HEALTH IMPLICATIONS AMONG PEOPLE IN DENSELY POPULATED LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREAS IN GOMBE STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Sound is very pleasant when it is within a tolerable limit and is very essential for communication in animals, including humans. However, when excessive; can cause harm to animals and humans. Regulations have been set to control excessive noise so as to safeguard the environment, so that it can be conducive to human survival and health. It was observed that due to the proliferation of

small-scale industries located in residential areas, higher noise levels are produced. Therefore, this study was designed to assess the noise pollution and the perceived health implications among people in densely populated Local Government Areas of Gombe State, Nigeria. A mixed method of concurrent type was adopted for the study. Instruments used for data collection were a decibel meter (Sound Level Monitor) and an unstructured interview. Results revealed that higher sounds mean higher than the permissible limit of 85.3dB, from Dukku, 76.6dB from Gombe metropolis and 62.8dB from Kantungo were observed. It was concluded that the noise observed in the study area was higher than the permissible limit of 60dB for residential plus small-scale industries and commercial areas which reflects pollution. A lack of knowledge of the health effects of long exposure to excessive noise among the respondents was observed. However, the respondent revealed that after a prolonged stay in excessive noise, they experience a high level of stress, tiredness, headache and disrupted sleep. Therefore, a policy should be formulated by the government to reduce small-scale production and commerce in residential locations.

KEYWORDS: Assessment, Noise, Pollution, Health, Implications

INTRODUCTION

Sound is the main source of communication in many animals, including human beings. Sound, when it is low, is pleasant and harmless. However, a loud, unpleasant or unwanted sound is called a noise and constitutes pollution. Noise (La. *Nausea*=*seasickness*) is a physical form of pollution which is not harmful to the air, soil and water but can affect the health of animals, including human beings. Noise pollution is unwanted or excessive noise that can have a deleterious effect on human health, wildlife and environmental quality (Britannica, 2026). It has also been defined by My Hearing Centres (2024) as the presence of excessive or disruptive sound in the environment. The author further pointed out that noise pollution can be sourced from transportation, construction, industrial activity and social events. According to Envira (2023), environmental noise pollution is defined as the presence in the environment of noise or vibration, whatever the acoustic emitter that originate them which implies annoyance, risk, or damage to people to the development of their activities or to good of nature, even when their effect is to disturb the enjoyment of sounds of natural origin, or which cause significant effects on the environment.

Noise level is measured in decibels (dB). The permissible limit for residential area, as posited by National Environmental Standard and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) (2009), it was 50 for daytime and 35dB for night, for mixed residential and small-scale production and commercial area is 60dB for daytime and 50 for nighttime. For the industrial area outside the perimeter fence, NESREA (2009) pointed out that the permissible limit is 70dB for daytime, while 60dB for nighttime.

Living in a noisy environment above the permissible limit can generate health consequences, as averred by National Geographic (2026), indicating that noise pollution can cause hearing loss, stress, and high blood pressure. In the same vein, My Hearing Centres (2024) included hearing loss, sleep disturbance, increased stress and cardiovascular problems as consequences of noise pollution. Also, children who live near noisy environments have been found to suffer from stress and other health problems, such as impairment of memory, level of attention and reading skills (National Geographic, 2026).

In the study of Godson et al. (2009) on assessment of noise pollution and the associated health problems in selected secondary schools, the study revealed that the noise level ranged from 68.3 to 84.7 db. Over 60% of the respondents reported that vehicular moment was the major source of the noise. The study further revealed that tiredness and lack of school concentration were the major

health challenges experienced by the respondents. In the same vein, another study also revealed that significant noise pollution was observed above the permissible limit; the result further revealed a non-significant level of knowledge among the respondents, despite the residents being youth (Muzammil et al., 2024). The study of Oladije et al. (2025) reported a noise level above a permissible limit; the noise levels reported in the study were 86.78 and 83.16. The study further reported that the health challenges experienced by the respondents were birth complications, cardiovascular problems, sleep disturbance and muscle tension.

Similarly, the study of Alasmar (2023) reported that the respondents revealed a significant exposure which significantly affects their physiological and psychological health. In the study of Kumar (2023), the respondents were exposed to high-level noise exceeding the permissible limit, and the health challenges reported by the respondents were pain in the ear, rise in blood pressure, loss of sleep, whistling and buzzing in the ear and headache. The result of the study of Okwudili (2025) revealed that the noise level observed from the study area ranged from 79.4 to 95.8 dB, and the cumulative mean for the eight wards ranged from 87.0 to 91.2 db all of which were significant at .05 above the acceptable range.

- **Statement of Problems**

The source of shelter, clothes for humans and animals are all from the environment. However, the activities of man, such as mining, agricultural processing, and processing of materials for shelter and food, degrade the environment through the generation of pollutants, which adversely affect the health of both plants and animals in the environment. The Federal Government of Nigeria, through its agencies such as Nirsal Microfinance Bank, Bank of Industry, and Development Bank of Nigeria, disburses huge amounts of funds to small-scale industries to boost their activities; this resulted in the proliferation of small-scale industries operating in commercial and residential areas throughout Nigeria. The activities of such industries generate waste in the form of chemicals, water, smoke and noise, which, due to poor management, result in environmental pollution. It was observed that there increased small-scale industries which carries their activity mostly in residential locations. Therefore, this study was designed to assess noise pollution and the perceived health implications among people in densely populated Local Government Areas in Gombe State, Nigeria.

- **Objective of the Study**

The objective of the study was to examine the noise pollution level and the associated health implications as perceived by people residing in densely populated Local Government Areas in Gombe State, specifically to:

- i. Find out the level of noise pollution in densely populated Local Government Areas in Gombe State
- ii. Assess the perceived health implications among people residing in densely populated Local Government Areas in Gombe State.

- **Research Question**

The following research questions were raised and answered in the study:

- i. What is the level of noise pollution in the selected LGAs in Gombe State?

- ii. What is the perception of people residing in selected LGAs in Gombe State on the health implications of noise pollution in Gombe State?

METHODS AND MATERIALS

The research design adopted for this study was a mixed method of concurrent type. A survey was conducted using a Sound Level Monitor (Decibel Meter) to assess the level of noise in randomly selected sites in each of the selected Local Government Areas, while an interview was conducted to evaluate the perceived health implications of noise pollution among the respondents. The cluster sampling technique was used to group all the LGAs in the three senatorial zones of Gombe state. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the most densely populated LGAs in all three senatorial zones, one from each of the senatorial zones. The Local Government selected for the study were Dukku with the total population 347,700, Gombe with the population of 446,800 and Kaltungo with the population of 268,600 (CITY POPULATION, 2022). Interviews were conducted on randomly selected people residing in the selected LGAs in the State.

RESULTS

The findings are presented in table as follows:

Research Question 1: What is the level of noise pollution in Gombe State, Nigeria

Table 1: Sound Level Detected using Decibel Meter in Three Local Government Areas of Gombe State

LGAs	Sites	First (dB)	Second (dB)	Third (dB)	Average (dB)
1. Dukku	1	74.5	90.7	88.5	84.5
	2	77.9	91.9	82.3	84.0
	3	77.8	92.0	92.4	87.4
	Average (dB)	76.7	91.5	87.7	85.3
2. Gombe	1	83.0	70.4	85.6	79.6
	2	97.7	77.3	59.6	78.2
	3	73.6	82.0	60.4	72.0
	Average (dB)	84.7	76.5	68.5	76.6
3. Kaltungo	1	63.9	54.0	68.1	62.0
	2	66.9	52.4	72.4	63.8
	3	69.8	51.1	67.3	62.7
	Average (dB)	66.8	52.5	69.2	62.8

Table 1 revealed the sound level detected using a decibel meter in three LGAs of Gombe State, collected in residential and small-scale industrial and commercial locations. The table shows that all the parameters collected were above the permissible limit set by NESREA (2009). The table shows a significant noise pollution with the highest from Dukku town with the average of 85.3dB, followed by Gombe metropolis with the average of 76.6dB, and the least from Kaltungo with the average of 62.8dB. This showed a significant noise pollution capable of causing harm to animals and human health.

Research question 2: What is the perception of the people residing in Gombe State on the health effects of noise pollution?

Based on the interview conducted among the people randomly interviewed for the study, a lack of knowledge of harm that may result from exposure to excessive noise, the common response noted from the respondents was a feeling of being disturbed. The interviewees reported that they experienced serious stress after exposure to high noise for a long period of time, trembling in the ear, and interference with sleep.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding shows significant noise pollution in the study area. The finding is similar to that of Godson et al. (2009) on assessment of noise pollution and the associated health problems in selected secondary schools. The study revealed that the noise level ranged from 68.3 to 84.7 dB above the permissible limit. In the same vein, the study of Muzammil et al. (2024) revealed that significant noise pollution was observed above the permissible limit; the result further revealed a non-significant knowledge among the respondents, despite the residents being young. Similarly, the study of Oladije et al. (2025) reported a noise above a permissible limit; the noise level reported in the study was 86.78 and 83.16dB, which is also above the permissible limit.

The study further reported that the health challenges experienced by the respondents were birth complications, cardiovascular problems, sleep disturbance and muscle tension. Similarly, the study of Alasmar (2023) reported that the respondents revealed a significant exposure to a noisy environment with significant effects on their physiological and psychological health. In the study of Kumar (2023), the respondents were exposed to high-level noise exceeding the permissible limit, and the health challenges reported by the respondents were pain in the ear, rise in blood pressure, loss of sleep, whistling and buzzing in the ear and headache. The result of the study of Okwudili (2025) revealed that the noise level observed from the study area ranged from 79.4 to 95.8dB, and the cumulative mean for the eight wards ranged from 87.0 to 91.2dB, all of which were significant at .05 above the acceptable range.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Noise was observed in the study area, higher than the permissible limit, which reflects pollution. A lack of knowledge of the health effects of long exposure to excessive noise among the respondents was observed. However, the respondent revealed that after a prolonged stay in excessively noisy area, they experience a high level of stress, tiredness, headache and disrupted sleep; however, these challenges were linked to work by the respondents, not exposure to the noise. Therefore, a policy should be formulated by the government to reduce small-scale production and commercial activities in residential location. Also, sensitization is required on the health effects of noise to people residing in the study area; this will go a long way in managing the noise, thereby reducing its effects on the health of the residents.

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